

Ethnozoological Practices of Vertebrate Origin Among Tiwa Tribe in Nagaon District, Assam

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Plants and animals have been used as medicine in ancient times and are continued in many different communities of people. The present study deals with the traditional use of vertebrate animals to treat diseases among Tiwa tribe of Nagaon district, Assam. It is primarily based on field surveys carried out in different villages and information collected from local people about animal species used as medicine, body parts used, methods to prepare the remedies, and for which ailments and their prescription.

The survey showed 25 species of vertebrate used in Tiwa tribe to heal diseases out of which 44% are mammal, 24% pisces, 20% aves, 8% reptiles and 4% amphibia. Animal and animal parts like skin, nail, flesh, oil etc are used to prepare medicine traditionally. Domestic and wild animals are used for medicinal purposes, example: pigs, cows, goats, foxes, bats, toads, snakes, fish, etc.

By the use of animal-derived medicine, the people of Tiwa tribe were able to cure many common human diseases like - tuberculosis, malaria, skin diseases, piles, dysentery, eczema, body pain, asthma, stomach disorders, paralysis, etc.

The values of animal-based medicine are very important in tribal culture. Due to the threat to those animals, there is now a restriction on using animals and their parts to make medicines. But this traditional knowledge is passed on from generation to generation and it is our duty to preserve it as it will further help in developing new medicine and improve medical science.

Keywords: Tiwa tribe, tribal, animal, vertebrate, medicine, remedy, traditional, cure.